

PIONEERING SUSTAINABLE CRM RECOVERY IN EUROPEAN MINING

Europe's mining industry faces a major challenge: recovering critical raw materials (CRMs) from complex, low-grade ores.

OPTIMINER tackles this with sustainable, tech-driven solutions that balance environmental and financial goals.

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PILOT MINES

SPAIN
SALORO and
LEONORE

GREECE
TERNA MAG

POLAND
JSW

FINLAND
TAPOJÄRVI

CHILE
MINERA
HASPAREN SPA

FOCUS ON CRMs

12
Mg
Magnesium

74
W
Tungsten

60
Nd
Neodymium

29
Cu
Copper

27
Co
Cobalt

6
C
Coal

Funded by the European Union

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AFFILIATED ENTITIES

